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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
4	D4.1	D21	Networking Event for Early Career Researchers #1	CU

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Other	Public	D4.1

Description (short)
<p>The ENLIGHT “Research and Innovation agenda with and for Society” (RISE) project aims at establishing foundations and initiating implementation of a common research and innovation (R&I) agenda within the ENLIGHT European University Alliance.</p> <p>Work package 4 has two specific projects. 4.1 To plan a series of events to support networking/leadership skills for early career researchers (ECRs) and 4.2 is the Researcher Assessment working group.</p> <p>The first event, for 4.1 work package, was held on Tuesday 25th October 2022 between 12:00-14:00 CET, entitled ‘Networking Skills for Early Career Researchers’ and was held online.</p> <p>Professor Jane Walsh, University of Galway, and Dr. Janka Kottulová, Comenius University Bratislava, were the guest presenters.</p>

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Abbreviations

ENLIGHT partner	Short Name	Country
University of Bordeaux	UBx	FR
Ghent University	UGent	BE
Comenius University Bratislava	CU	SK
University of the Basque Country	UPV/EHU	ES
University of Galway	Gal	IE
University of Göttingen	UGOE	DE
University of Groningen	RUG	NL
University of Tartu	UT	EE
Uppsala University	UU	SE

1. Project background

As outlined in the project description the aim of ENLIGHT RISE is to *'enable a world-class joint R&I agenda within ENLIGHT RISE we will need to ATTRACT AND RETAIN THE BEST RESEARCHERS in Europe and beyond, while promoting an inclusive leadership culture in keeping with the broader mission of ENLIGHT'*.

Work package 4 is led by Comenius University Bratislava (CU) with co-leads Ghent University and University of Galway.

To develop attractive career frameworks for researchers we will launch strong complementary actions to support early career development within the alliance through **networking, mentoring and leadership training**. One of the key engagements of ENLIGHT is to create a balanced network across different social, economic and geographic areas in Europe, with careful attention to the way expertise and opportunities are shared across the network, and to develop a supportive structure for talent development, career guidance, and business ideas.

ENLIGHT RISE will nurture its human capital, a key foundation for a competitive joint R&I agenda. Building on the **ENLIGHT doctoral network's skills** workshops (part of the ENLIGHT Erasmus+ project), we will expand to create a **network of early career researchers** (post-docs, early-career faculty, <10 yrs. from PhD), to foster fruitful research collaborations on the ENLIGHT flagship challenges and stimulate research mobility. It is envisaged that the researcher digital matching tool (WP1) will facilitate the matching of researchers from different universities and at different stages of their careers.

It was planned to organise **annual early career researcher networking events** satellite to the ENLIGHT European Dialogues, bringing together the ENLIGHT doctoral network and early career researcher network but the impact of Covid/delayed events has had an impact on this original plan.

The first event was planned to take place in M12, August 2022, but it was felt that the timing was not attractive so a two month extension was applied for in order to plan/host the event by end October 2022 when the envisioned target group would not be on holidays or during the mayhem of university re-openings in September/early October.

2. Event Planning

As with all planning of events, the team lead and co-leads of the work group discussed topics/options for the planned event and in consultation with the other members of the working group from the other 6 universities the decisions were taken on/to

- Hold the event online
- Date of event: 25 October 2022
- Topic – 'Networking Skills for Early Career Researchers'
- Duration of event – 2 hours
- Communications strategy
- Presenters – agreed that team leads would source speakers
- Registration/event management/feedback etc. – was agreed to be managed by Galway.

Professor Jane Walsh, University of Galway and Dr Janka Kottulová, Comenius University Bratislava, were identified by the leads as the two most suitable guest speakers. A registration portal was created, and the event would be held using zoom.

For the purpose of promoting the event, an event flyer was created using the ENLIGHT template. A meeting of all the WP 4.1 was held on 19th October to ensure communications between all the partners was agreed and to allow any questions from members. It was agreed that PhD researchers could attend the events of WP 4.1 but that WP 4.2 was tailored only to those post-PhD researchers as per the project guidelines. It was also agreed at this meeting that we would include a question of attendees to help determine topics for future events in support of ENLIGHT.

3. Communications/Promotion

Firstly, the event flyer was sent via email to all 9 universities within the alliance for their internal distribution. Universities were responsible for their own internal promotion of the event.

The ENLIGHT communications team promoted the event via the ENLIGHT website, calendar and social media channels.

<https://enlight-eu.org/university-about-us/news-events/640-networking-skills-for-early-career-researchers-25th-october-2022>

Reminders were sent to the partner universities to include numbers of registrations by university in the week preceding the event.

An event reminder was sent to all those registered the day before the event.

4. Speakers

Team leads from Galway and Comenius identified the two guest speakers.

Professor Jane Walsh is a Health Psychologist and Director of the Mobile Technology and Health (mHealth) Research Group at the University of Galway where she leads a programme of research on personalised connected health.

- Jane leads and partners on projects worth €15 million euro funded by Horizon 2020, HRB and SFI;
- Is the Co-Leader of the Health and Wellbeing Cluster in the Whitaker Institute and a member of the Irish Cancer Society Research Advisory Board;
- Was recently appointed to the Royal Irish Academy Social Sciences Committee and is a former Chair of the Psychological Society of Ireland (PSI) Division of Health Psychology;
- Recent recipient of the University of Galway President's Award for Research Excellence (2020) in recognition of her work.

Janka Kottulová, PhD. works as a researcher at the Centre for Gender Studies at the Faculty of Arts, Comenius University.

- Janka leads the CU team participating in the [Equal4Europe](#) project and supports the implementation of institutional gender equality plan at the Comenius University Bratislava;
- She worked as a lecturer at the Faculty of Management, Comenius University for almost ten years;

- As project manager at SAIA (Slovak Academic Information Agency) she is involved in projects focusing on career development of researchers and intersectoral collaborations to support it.

5. Event Data

Registrations by 24th October 2022 **195**

UPV/EHS	UBx	CU	Gal	UGent	UGOE	UG	UT	UU	Other*
19	20	18	34	6	7	13	14	1	63

* Other: People who registered using personal email accounts and didn't specify University choice.

Attendees on 25th October 2022.

As per initial zoom report **106** was the maximum number of attendees who attended the online event. There were some last minute cancellation notices and requests for the audio recording post event.

A poll was conducted during the first 10 minutes of the event to pose three questions;

- To which university do you belong?
- Job title most closely resembles your work?
- To gauge current networking experience.

Poll feedback

To which university do you belong?

UPV/EHS	UBx	CU	Gal	UGent	UGOE	UG	UT	UU	Other*
17.2%	15.5%	5%	14%	0%	14%	7%	10.3%	2%	8.6%

Job title – responses

PhD Researcher (R1)	Postdoctoral Researcher (R2)	Research Fellow (R3)	Professional support staff	Academic position	Other
45%	29.3%	5.2%	1.5%	15.5%	3.4%

How do you rate your current networking skills?

Excellent – I love meeting new people and networking	7%
Good – I like meeting new people and I'm ok with networking	31%
Average – I network when I have to for work purposes	40%

Poor – I'm not a fan of networking and don't like going up to people I've never met before	22%
Very poor – I detest the very thought of it	0%

Event schedule:

- 1200 – 1210 Opening introductions/allowing time for people to join/open polls/request to record event**
- 1210 – 1215 Brief introduction to ENLIGHT by organiser**
- 1215 – 1245 Professor Jane Walsh, Networking experience and tips for Early Career Researchers**
- 1245 – 1255 Q&A**
- 1255 – 1305 Breakout room – all participants, working in pairs, practiced introductions**
- 1310 – 1340 Dr Janka Kottulová, 'How to network effectively'.**
- 1340 – 1345 Q&A**
- 1350 Closing comments and distribution of feedback questionnaire.**

6. Feedback post event

A feedback form/QR code was given to all attendees towards the end of the session. The feedback form/link was also sent to participants post event. 38 Responses were received which is circa 38% of attendees (less administrators). The following questions were put to the attendees.

To which university do you belong?

UPV/EHS	UBx	CU	Gal	UGent	UGOE	UG	UT	UU	Other*
15.8%	26%	10.5%	15.8%	2.6%	5%	5%	8%	0%	10.5%

To which job area/title do you most closely align?

PhD Researcher	Postdoctoral Researcher	Research Fellow	Academic staff
58%	29%	5%	8%

Gender.

Female	Male	Blank
53%	34%	13%

On a scale of 1 to 5 (5 being the highest) how would you rate this workshop?

5	4	3	2	1
32%	53%	16%	0%	0%

List 1-3 things you found most useful about this event?

Feedback (26 replies) on this question was very useful and **sharing of personal experiences** was found to be the most popular, followed by **tips** and the **Q&A** section. The team will analyse this feedback in more detail and use for planning future events.

What do you think could have made this event better?

Mixed responses to this question (21 replies) with some requests for 'in-person' events, more break-out rooms, more similar events.

What other events would you like to recommend as part of this Leadership Skills programme?

● Networking	21
● Mentoring (mentor and mentee...	15
● Building research collaborations	26
● How to manage research teams	14
● Communicating your research	22
● Career planning - within academe...	20
● Career planning - beyond academe...	17
● Other	0

Under the category marked 'other' respondents were asked to recommend their own choices.

- Science communication and how to become visible
- Plan an alternative path to professorship in academia
- Event or workshop on social media promotion and research profile build
- Interviewing for academic positions
- Probably, it is better to add more information about grant application and seeking
- Summer schools/special conferences for rehearsing networking and speeches maybe
- How to find funding support internally and externally, i.e., what's available where you work and beyond.
- Build research collaborations.

7. Recommendations and lessons learned.

The meeting of WP4.1, pursuant to the event of 25th October, met online to review event details and feedback from the event.

The post event report had been circulated to the group and a brief synopsis of the event was delivered by University of Galway co-lead.

The group reviewed the data of how many registrations (195) vs number of attendances (106) and felt that unfortunately this was not unusual for online events in their experiences.

The number of participants dropped to 72 post break-out rooms.

When reviewing the feedback some participants reported lack of audio/visual technology at their end and this was outside the control of the event organisers.

The group was quite pleased with the number of participant feedback (43) which is considered quite high and we will use this feedback/suggestions when planning future events.

45% of participants were in the PhD category so we will endeavour to keep similar events open to this group of early career researchers as much as possible. The next highest group were Postdoctoral researchers at nearly 30%.

There was some difficulty experienced by partners who reported communications issues in promoting the event and some found it hard to access via ENLIGHT website.

Data from the feedback is already contained within the report and the group discussed how we could use such information for planning future events and the two main areas of focus are 1. Timing and 2. To host the event online or in-person.

- Timing: Next event will need to be organized before month 24 (August 2023).
- Online or In-person: There is a preference for in-person events, but the group will look at options to plan this event perhaps attached to another, larger event as it is felt there is not enough budget/accessibility to have people travel to a short event like this one (half-day).